

DESIGN OPTIMISATION OF 3D WOVEN T-JOINT REINFORCEMENTS

Shibo Yan¹, Andrew Long² and Xuesen Zeng³

¹ Polymer Composites Group, Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham NG7 2RD, UK Email: shibo.yan@nottingham.ac.uk

² Polymer Composites Group, Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham NG7 2RD, UK, Email: andrew.long@nottingham.ac.uk

³ Centre for Future Materials, University of Southern Queensland, West Street Toowoomba 4350, Queensland, Australia, Email: xuesen.zeng@usq.edu.au

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ABSTRACT

To facilitate the design of 3D woven composite T-joint preforms, the effects of fibre architecture variations on mechanical performance under tensile pull-off loading were studied, based on the FE modelling framework proposed in a previous study. In search of the optimum fibre architecture, the study was restricted to only vary the path of weft yarns at the junction of the T-joints, as this maintains quasi-constant fibre volume fraction for the composites and does not require any modification on the weaving machine producing the preforms from that used for the two types of T-joint specimens tested previously. A comprehensive search for the optimum preform design for the T-joint composite would require a tremendous amount of computational resources when evaluating the mechanical performance of the individuals, even using a highly efficient optimisation algorithm. Inspired by the weave patterns of the two types of T-joint specimen, the problem was simplified by grouping the weft yarn arrangements into three basic design variables. Quantified by the proportions of design variables at the junction of the 3D woven T-joints, new weave pattern variations were designed and analysed. Finally, a design optimisation philosophy for 3D woven T-joint reinforcements under tensile pull-off loading is given.

1 INTRODUCTION

3D woven composites have recently been used to address the growing need for weight reduction and high performance facing the aerospace industry, when laminated composites, cannot meet these requirements due to low interlaminar strength. For instance, the applications of 3D woven composites in the fan blade of LEAP engine [1] and the brace of B787 landing gear [2] see the advantages of these materials, including strengthened through-thickness properties, high delamination resistance and near net shape manufacturing.

The design space of 3D woven composites, specifically for those with geometric features, is very large as the design is no longer only limited to ply orientations and thicknesses, but also a wide range of weave patterns in their 3D architectures. Additionally, it was found in a previous study [3] that limited weave variation in the 3D woven reinforcements resulting from opening different sheds when inserting weft yarns (Figure 1) could lead to a significant difference in the mechanical performance, e.g. a more than 100% difference in the ultimate strength, through the tensile pull-off tests on two types of 3D woven T-joints [3], which further improves the challenges for designing the optimum 3D woven reinforcement.

With the desire to promote the applications of 3D woven T-joints in the aerostructures, this paper aims to understand the effects of 3D reinforcement architecture on mechanical behaviour of 3D woven T-joints under pull-off loading. Newly designed T-joint models are evaluated using the same procedure as proposed in [4] for simulating the quasi-static tensile pull-off test, and results are

compared with those of the two 3D woven T-joint models in the previous study [4] to relate variability of mechanical responses to weave variations. Finally, a design optimisation philosophy for 3D woven T-joint reinforcements under tensile pull-off loading is given.

Figure 1: Images from μ CT scan of the two types of 3D preform showing the weave variation at the junction: (a) type 1; (b) type 2; section views show the weave pattern (orthogonal) at web and flange.

2 BASIC DESIGN VARIABLES

In quest of the optimum fibre architecture, it was restricted to only vary the path of the weft yarns in the junction of the T-joints, as this maintain quasi-constant fibre volume fraction and does not require any modification on the weaving machine producing the preforms for the T-joint specimens tested in the previous study, even though the number of variations could be up to 3.6 million. This computation demanding problem was simplified by grouping the weft yarn arrangement into three basic design variables: yarn path straightness, yarn path entanglement and yarn path cross-over, where yarn path straightness and yarn path entanglement are mutually exclusive.

2.1 Yarn path straightness

If a weft yarn stays in its own layer or parallel to its neighbouring weft yarn within the same weft yarn stack throughout the preform, i.e. from web through radius to flange, this is referred to as yarn path straightness. In this case, the weft yarns are stacked on each other in the form of a UD laminate, with an advantage of largely reduced crimp in the weft yarn path. For example, all the weft yarn in 3D woven type 1 model maintain yarn path straightness. Yarn path straightness can make the most of yarn axial modulus and therefore enable a higher effective modulus in the direction along the flange, which eventually might lead to a stiffer mechanical response in the tensile pull-off tests.

2.2 Yarn path entanglement

Contrary to yarn path straightness, when the neighbouring weft yarns are not parallel to each other throughout the preform, those yarns will be entangled together at the location where the yarn path changes, and this is referred to as yarn path entanglement. Yarn path entanglement is defined between at least two neighbouring weft yarns. Yarn path entanglement changes the geometric feature of the weft yarns from a laminate-like to an inter-woven fibre architecture, which might be less vulnerable to failure when subjected to loading in the through-thickness direction.

2.3 Yarn path cross-over

The preform reinforcing the 3D woven composite T-joint was initially woven flat and then folded into a T shape with an equal number of weft yarns in each half of the preform. If a weft yarn does not always stay in the same half of the preform, i.e. it goes across to the other half of the preform when it comes to the flange, it is referred to as yarn path cross-over. Yarn path cross-over determines the fibre architecture and further influences the stress distribution around the noodle area.

3 QUANTIFICATION OF WEFT YARN PATH VARIATIONS

After categorizing the arrangement of the weft yarns at the junction, new weave pattern variations for the T-joint can be quantified by the basic design variables introduced above. As yarn path straightness and yarn path entanglement are mutually exclusive, there are only two independent design variables for the preform, including yarn path cross-over. Consequently, quantification of a weave pattern variation can be addressed by specifying the proportions of weft yarns in the design variable categories through the following notation: ($_ \%C, _ \%E/ _ \%S$), in which $\%C$ denotes the proportion of weft yarns that have yarn path cross-over; $\%E$ denotes the proportion of weft yarns that have yarn path entanglement; $\%S$ denotes the proportion of weft yarns that have yarn path straightness, and $\%S = 100 - \%E$ according to mutual exclusivity. For instance, as shown in Figure 2, the weave pattern for 3D woven type 1 T-joint (hereafter named 3Dv1) does not have yarn path cross-over and entanglement, so it can be described as $(0\%C + 0\%E/100\%S)$. Similarly, the weave pattern for 3D woven type 2 T-joint (hereafter named 3Dv2) is denoted by $(100\%C + 100\%E/0\%S)$, as all the weft yarns have crossed over to the other half and entangled among one another.

Figure 2: Schematic weave pattern of 3Dv1 (left), 3Dv2 (right) highlighting design variable proportions.

4 NEW WEAVE PATTERNS

6 new weave patterns for the 3D woven T-joint were designed, by varying the path of weft yarns around the noodle area. As the weave patterns for 3Dv1 and 3Dv2 specimens are the two endpoints of the proportion intervals of yarn path cross-over and entanglement, the design of new weave patterns aims to decouple the two design variables, by varying only one design variable at a time, to determine the effects of each single variable on mechanical performance. All variations were quantified by the proportions of yarn path entanglement (straightness) and yarn path cross-over. The 6 new weave patterns were named 3Dv3 to 3Dv8, and the schematic weave patterns showing the weave variations can be found in Figure 3. Note that a simple way to track the change of weft yarn path is to compare the numbering of the weft yarns (1 to 5, and 1' to 5') at the web with those at the flange of the preform.

Figure 3: Schematic wave pattern of 3Dv3 to 3Dv8 (right) highlighting design variable proportions.

5 RESULTS

The 6 newly designed 3D woven T-joint models were numerically tested using the same procedure as proposed in [4,5] for simulating the quasi-static tensile pull-off test for 3Dv1 and 3Dv2 specimens, and all material properties are consistent with those used for the T-joint specimens. The predicted results of the 6 new 3D woven T-joint models along with those of the 3Dv1 and 3Dv2 models were compared together in terms of structural stiffness and failure load. As the proposed modelling

approach could not capture the full failure process of the specimens [5], and the existence of nonlinearity in the structural stiffness, the stiffness is defined as that at a displacement of 0.35 mm, at which stage macroscopic damage has not yet initiated. The failure load is defined as an average value between 1.5 mm to 1.6 mm in displacement, to capture the effects of damage given that final failure load is likely to be unreliable as discussed in [5]. An illustration for the definition of the compared structural stiffness and failure load of the T-joint models is given in Figure 4.

The predicted stiffnesses and failure loads of all 8 T-joint models are plotted in Figure 4 with 3Dv1 and 3Dv2 validated against experimental results. Distinct differences in the stiffness and failure loads are shown between these 3D woven T-joint models with only weave variations at the junction. The maximum difference in the stiffness, i.e. between 3Dv7 and 3Dv4, is 15.2%, whilst the maximum difference in the failure load, i.e. between 3Dv1 and 3Dv4, is 30%. Note that in the experiment the ultimate strength of 3Dv2 can be 100% more than that of 3Dv1. In addition, the influence of fibre architecture at the junction of the 3D woven T-joint models on stiffness is not as significant as that on failure behaviour. The varied mechanical behaviour resulting from the variations in the fibre architectures of the 3D woven T-joint models show the performance characteristic of 3D woven composites can be tailored, which is an advantage of such materials but analysis techniques that are able to accurately predict the resulting structural performance for the 3D fibre architectures are also needed at the design stage for composite structures.

Figure 4: Comparison of predicted structural stiffness and failure load of the 3D woven T-joint models, with 3Dv1 and 3Dv2 validated against experimental results.

5.1 Damage resistance capability of the 3D woven T-joint models

As the compared failure load of each T-joint model is defined at a displacement between 1.5 mm and 1.6 mm, it thus could not accurately represent the ultimate strength of the T-joints, which is mostly dominated by the damage resistance capability as there is only a minor difference in the initial stiffness of the T-joints. At a displacement of around 1.5 mm, which is not close to that for the ultimate strength as observed in the experiments for 3Dv1 and 3Dv2, the defined failure load is still partially affected by the inherent stiffness, rather than solely reflecting the damage resistance capability. If a T-joint model is inherently stiffer but weaker (in terms of ultimate strength) than another T-joint because of the variation in the fibre architectures, the defined failure load for the stiffer but weaker T-joint model could also be higher if no catastrophic damage has occurred at the displacement between 1.5 mm and 1.6 mm, due to the elastic contribution to the failure load. In order to decouple this contribution from the defined failure load, the equivalent failure loads relative to 3Dv1 are computed for the other 7 T-joint models (Figure 4), which are defined by assuming they have the same damage resistance capability as 3Dv1 but retain their own stiffness as below:

$$FL_i^{equi} = \frac{ST_i}{ST_{3Dv1}} FL_{3Dv1} \quad (1)$$

where FL represents the failure load; ST denotes the stiffness; subscript i ranges from 3Dv1 to 3Dv8 denoting each T-joint model, and superscript equi denotes equivalent failure load to 3Dv1.

Therefore the difference between the failure load and equivalent failure load relative to 3Dv1, as illustrated in Figure 4, is the extra damage resistance capability with respect to 3Dv1 that the specific fibre architecture of each T-joint model offers. It is noted that the distribution of the extra damage resistance capability of the T-joint models is roughly consistent with trend for the defined failure load, except 3Dv4 which shows a lower extra damage resistance capability than 3Dv2, after decoupling the stiffness contribution. This means that the slightly higher failure load of 3Dv4 is mostly due to its higher stiffness, and in fact it may have accumulated more damage than 3Dv2, which is likely to achieve a higher ultimate strength. Therefore, the extent of damage in terms of interface and constituent materials of each T-joint model was investigated. The interface damage is quantified by the ratio of the damaged nodes, whose damage parameter (Abaqus notation: CSDMG) is greater than 0, to the total number of nodes at the interface. In addition, an interface damage ratio for damage parameter (Abaqus notation: CSDMG) greater than or equal to 0.9 (full damage occurs at the value of 1) is used to characterise the proportion of severely damaged interface. Meanwhile, the constituent material damage ratio is defined as the ratio of damaged matrix and yarn elements with stiffness penalty factor P , full damage occurs at the value of 0.001) less than 1 in terms of all types of failure modes, to the total number of elements in the model [5]. Similarly, an additional material damage ratio for P less than or equal to 0.7 is employed to evaluate the proportion of the damaged materials whose moduli have been degraded to less than or equal to 70% of the values of the intact materials. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the comparisons of interface damage ratios and the constituent material damage ratios of the T-joint models respectively, at the same displacement of 1.57 mm.

Based on Figure 5 and Figure 6, the damage extent within the T-joint model appears to be able to represent the extra damage resistance capability deduced in Figure 4. In general, a T-joint model with lower extra damage resistance capability was shown to have higher material damage ratios and vice versa. It is also found that the damage resistance capability is collectively affected by damage at the interface and constituent materials. For instance, although 3Dv3 had a low percentage of interfacial damage, it did not achieve a high failure load due to its high damage ratio in the constituent materials. The observation that more damage accumulated in 3Dv4 than 3Dv2 as implied from the above damage resistance analysis is validated by the damage ratios. It should be noted that the use of the specific damage ratios is only a method to sample the extent of damage in the T-joint models, which is difficult to quantify accurately due to the complex damage behaviour of 3D woven composites.

Figure 5: Comparison of interface damage ratios in the 3D woven T-joint models at displacement of 1.57 mm.

Figure 6: Comparison of constituent material damage ratios in the 3D woven T-joint models at displacement of 1.57 mm.

5.2 Effects of yarn path crossover on stiffness and failure load

In order to determine the effects of each single design variable on mechanical performance of the T-joint models, some of the new weave patterns were designed to have the same percentage in either of the two design variables. Through analysing the results of the T-joint models which have the same proportion of yarn path entanglement but varied proportions in yarn path cross-over, the effects of yarn path entanglement can be decoupled. Based on all 8 T-joint models, direct comparisons can be made at the yarn path entanglement proportions of 0% and 100%.

By comparing the results of 3Dv7, 3Dv8 and 3Dv2 which have the same proportion of yarn path entanglement at 100% but different proportions of yarn path cross-over at 0%, 60% and 100% respectively, it is found that there is a monotonic improvement in the stiffness and failure load with the increase of yarn path cross-over proportion. Similarly, by comparing the results of 3Dv1 and 3Dv3, which have the same proportion of yarn path entanglement at 0%, but different proportions of yarn

path cross-over at 0% and 100% respectively, an increasing trend is shown in the stiffness and failure load after improving the yarn path cross-over proportion from 0% to 100%.

5.3 Effects of yarn path entanglement on stiffness and failure load

Similarly, the effects of yarn path entanglement on stiffness and failure load can be found by analysing the results of the T-joint models which have the same proportion of yarn path cross-over but varied proportions in yarn path entanglement. Based on all 8 T-joint models, direct comparisons can be made at yarn path entanglement proportions of 0% and 100%.

By comparing the results of 3Dv3, 3Dv6, 3Dv5 and 3Dv2, which have the same proportion of yarn path cross-over at 100% but different proportions of yarn path entanglement at 0%, 40%, 70% and 100% respectively, it is shown that increasing the proportion of yarn path entanglement leads to an increase and then a decrease of stiffness, and increasing yarn path entanglement proportion leads to a quasi-monotonic increase in failure load. By comparing the results of 3Dv1 and 3Dv7, which have the same proportion of yarn path cross-over at 0% but different proportions of yarn path entanglement at 0% and 100% respectively, it is observed that there is a minor decrease in the stiffness but a slight increase in the failure load after improving the yarn path entanglement proportion from 0% to 100%.

6 DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The initial stiffness of the T-joint is thus largely determined by the T-joint flange in bending, and fibre architecture at the junction could have a minor impact on it. This is supported by the fact that a maximum difference of 15.2% was observed in stiffness among the 8 T-joint models, which have the same fibre architecture in the flange but varied pattern at the junction. Conversely, the fibre architecture at the junction dominates the failure behaviour of the T-joint under the tensile pull-off testing and could lead to a step-change in the ultimate failure load by changing the failure mode, i.e. a more than 100% increase between the two different T-joint specimens tested experimentally, resulting only from the fibre architecture difference at the junction. Similar to laminated composites, the primary damage mechanism in the 3D woven composite T-joints is delamination between the bulk matrix and yarns. A typical orthogonal weave pattern for the composite T-joint, as seen in 3Dv1, can alleviate delamination by the presence of binder yarns when compared to the equivalent laminated specimen. However, if the delamination propagation is mostly arrested by further varying the fibre architecture at the junction rather than solely relying on the binders, the damage tolerance of the composites would be significantly improved.

The weft yarns take most of the loads under this specific tensile pull-off loading case. Using yarn path cross-over in the weft yarns was found to be an effective way to improve both the stiffness and failure load. It appears that the more yarn path cross-over that is introduced, the better damage resistance capability the T-joint can gain, as the noodle would be reinforced by the crossed weft yarns. The T-joint models without yarn path cross-over end up with a large noodle in the centre (e.g. 3Dv1, 3Dv7) and subsequently both performed badly in the analysis, which is consistent with a previous study showing that the noodle is a critical damage area for composite T-joints under the same loading scenario [6].

Increasing the proportion of yarn path entanglement can also improve the damage resistance capability. However, the noodle is still a critical failure region as yarn path entanglement does not change the noodle, so the damage resistance capability would not be enhanced as much as can be achieved by yarn path cross-over. On the contrary, increasing yarn path entanglement proportion leads to the reduction in the proportion of yarn path straightness and therefore the structural stiffness would be compromised due to crimp introduced by the entangled weft yarns. Slightly reducing the yarn entanglement proportion was found to improve the stiffness of the T-joint whilst maintaining a similar failure load, which might be preferred in engineering applications.

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